

Screening of some Cameroonian Plants for their Potential Antibacterial Activity against Human Pathogenic Bacteria

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants are geared towards the development of the new antibiotics and the use of medicinal plants in the treatment of infectious diseases. The aim of this study was to determine the antibacterial spectrum of ten Cameroonian medicinal plants traditionally used in treatment of typhoid fever and other infectious diseases. The antibacterial activities of the ten medicinal plants extracts against *Salmonella typhi* ATCC 6539, *S. paratyphi A* & *S. paratyphi B*, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC25922, *Enterococcus faecalis* ATCC 10541, *Escherichia coli* ATCC11775, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC 13883 were initially evaluated by well diffusion technique followed by microdilution technique, to determine the zones of inhibition and Minimum inhibition concentration (MIC). The results from the present study have shown that, out of 10 plants investigated, nine plants were found to have antibacterial activity against at least one of the bacteria strains tested with inhibition zones ranging from 7.5 to 24 mm at concentration of 40 mg/ml, 80 mg/ml and 160 mg/ml; with good effect at 160 mg/ml. *Enterococcus faecalis* was the most susceptible bacteria with 8 plant extracts inhibiting its growth. In comparison, seven plant extracts inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* respectively, six plant extracts inhibited the growth of *Salmonella typhi*, while *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was sensitive to five plant extracts, *S. paratyphi B* was sensitive to four plant extracts, whereas, three plant extracts inhibited the growth of *S. paratyphi A* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* respectively. The highest zones of inhibition diameter were obtained from *Senna alata* with diameter of 24, 23.5, 22.5, 19, 18.5 and 16.5 mm against *Salmonella paratyphi A*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *S. paratyphi B*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* respectively at 160 mg/ml; and from *Pseudarthria confertiflora* with diameter of 23.5 and 17 mm against *S. typhi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* respectively at the same concentration. The lowest MIC values 256 µg/ml was exhibited by the extract of *Pseudarthria confertiflora* against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and the lowest MBC was 1024 µg/ml exhibited by the extracts from *Carica papaya* against *Enterococcus faecalis*. *Senna alata* was particularly effective antibacterial agent being capable of inhibiting the growth of all eight bacteria. *Bidens pilosa*, *Carica papaya* and *Pseudarthria confertiflora* were also good antibacterial agents, each being capable of inhibiting the growth of the majority of bacteria tested. These plants could serve as a cheap source of antibacterial constituent for the treatment of infectious diseases.

Key words: Medicinal plants, infectious diseases, antibacterial

INTRODUCTION

Infectious diseases are world's leading cause of premature death, killing almost 50,000 people everyday [1]. Resistance to conventional antimicrobial agent is emerging in a wide variety of pathogens and multiple drug resistance is becoming resistance to diverse organisms such as *Salmonella typhi*, *S. paratyphi A*, *S. paratyphi B*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [2, 3, 4]. Other problems with various

conventional antibiotics include toxicity, high cost and low efficacy. These problems therefore necessitate a search for new antimicrobial substances from other sources including plants.

Medicinal plant drugs play a key role in health especially in the developing countries such as Cameroon. Medicinal plants are used to treat common diseases such as typhoid fever, paratyphoid infections and gastroenteritis diseases, currently due to the fact they are cheaper, available and believed to present fewer side effects. Medicinal plants have been used by

billions of people around the world for thousands of years to treat various diseases [5]. Actually, more than 80% of the population within developing countries relies on the use of medicinal plants for their primary healthcare due to their lower cost and time tested nature [6]. Medicinal plants have also been very vital in the development of conventional medicine; about 25% of the conventional medicine is derived from plants [7]. A large number of phytochemical belonging to several chemical classes have been shown to have inhibitory effects on all types of microorganisms *in vitro* [3]; and some plant extracts have shown activity on both gram negative and gram positive organisms [8]. In Cameroon, attention has been directed towards medicinal plant research to substantiate the claims of the cure made by traditional healers, thus providing scientific basis for their efficacy. These medicinal plants; *Acmella caulirhiza* (whole plant), *Aspilia africana* (leaves), *Bidens pilosa* (stem-leaves), *Crassocephalum mannii* (leaves), *Stereospermum accuminatissimum* (bark), *Carica papaya* (leaves), *Dioscorea dumetorum* (leaves), *Pseudarthria*

confertiflora (leaves), *Senna alata* (leave), and *Dissotis perkinsiae* (leaves) have been claimed by traditional medical practitioners in Cameroon to be effective when used for treatment of infectious diseases.

This paper report the *in vitro* antibacterial screening of the extracts of these ten medicinal plants against eight human pathogenic bacteria, hence to establish the type of effect produced and to identify plants with broad spectrum activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethnobotanical survey

Ten plants used in Bamboutos division in Cameroon, for treatment of typhoid fever were identified in collaboration with traditional healers and elderly people. The taxonomic identities of these plants were confirmed by the senior taxonomist at the Yaoundé National Herbarium and the voucher specimens were kept in the Department of Plant Biology University of Dschang. The ethnomedical information is reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Profile of the ten medicinal plants screened for antibacterial activity

Botanical name (family, genus, species) and voucher number	Vernacular named	Habit	Part of the plant used	Therapeutic use
Asteraceae				
<i>Acmella caulirhiza</i> Delile, 42040/HNC	Ehengui, Pento'o	Herb	Leaves, Stem	Wounds, diarrhoea, malaria, pneumonia, dysentery, teeth ache, gonorrhoea, skin infections, arthritis, rheumatism, urinary tract infections [38, 39, 40, 41].
<i>Aspilia africana</i> (Pers) C.D. Adams, 36018/HNC	Packben	Herb	Stem with leaves	Peptic ulcer, wounds [42]. Menstruation disorders, Malaria, abdominale pains, anemia, heamorrhages, facilitated delivery [41, 43].
<i>Bidens pilosa</i> Linn., 23651/SRF-Cam	Lietmik, Lipiliep, Metsemik	Herb	Whole plant	Headaches, cough, intestina worms, malaria, typhoid fever [41]. Diabetes, pains, bacteria infections, dysentery and pharyngitis [30].
<i>Crassocephalum mannii</i> (Hook. F) Milne-Redh, 7623/SRF-Cam	Kepang, Neponlou, Poupou	Shrub	Leaves	None reported in available literature
Bignoniaceae				

<i>Stereospermum accuminatissimum</i> K. Schum. 45705/HNC	Watefê	Tree	Bark	None reported in available literature
Caricaceae				
<i>Carica papaya</i> Linn. 18647/SRF-Cam	Papaye, popo'o	Tree	Leaves	Fever, skin infections, asthma, rhinitis [44]. Malaria, gonorrhoea, yellow fever, headaches, splenomegaly [41]. Sexual transmissible diseases [45].
Dioscoreaceae				
<i>Dioscorea dumetorum</i> (Kunth) Pax 24431/SRF-Cam	Leliock, Meliock, Neliock	Climber	Leaves	None reported in available literature
Fabaceae				
<i>Pseudarthria confertiflora</i> (A. Rich.) Bak. 17465/SRF-Cam	Not found	Herb	Leaves	None reported in available literature
<i>Senna alata</i> (Linn.) Roxb. 42258/HNC	Foupan	Shrub	Leaves	Digestive tract infections, intestina worms, typhoid fever, poison, hepatitis, yellow fever [41]. Skin deseases, gonorrhea [46]; abdominal pains, hypertension [47]. Wounds, virales infections [48].
Melastomataceae				
<i>Dissotis perkinsiae</i> Gilg. 24719 SRF-Cam	Neem	Tree	Leaves	None reported in available literature

Microbial strains

Fresh clinical strains of *Salmonella typhi* ATCC 6539, *S. paratyphi A* & *S. paratyphi B*, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC25922, *Enterococcus faecalis* ATCC 10541, *Escherichia coli* ATCC11775, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853 and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC 13883 were obtained from the Microbiology Laboratory, Department of Biochemistry, University of Dschang. All the strains were stored at 4°C temperature until use. These microorganisms' strains are usually implicated in many infectious diseases.

Preparation of plant extracts

Fresh plant material were washed with tap water, air dried at room temperature for 15-30 days, and then homogenized to fine powder. A sample (200 g) of each powdered plant material was soaked in ethanol (500 ml) for 48 h with constant stirring. The suspension was filtered through Whatman filter paper N° 1. The filtrate was concentrated under vacuum using a rotavapor

to obtain the dry ethanol extract and stored at 4°C until further use.

Antibacterial assay

Determination of inhibition diameter

The media were prepared according to the manufactures' standard, 38g/1000 ml of distilled water. The ethanolic extracts were dissolved in 10% dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and further diluted to obtain different concentrations (160 mg/ml, 80 mg/ml and 40 mg/ml). Negative control used was DMSO. Ciprofloxacin was used as positive reference standard having a concentration of 10 µl/ml for all bacterial strains. The organisms were maintained on nutrient agar plates and were revived for bioassay by subculturing in fresh nutrient agar for 24 h before being used. The agar wells diffusion method described by [9], was adopted. Briefly, nutrient agar was prepared by autoclaving and allowed to cool to 40-50°C before seeded with the tested organism (in sterile petri-dishes of 90 mm diameter). The seeded plates were allowed to set and

cylindrical plugs were removed from the agar plates by means of a cork borer to procure wells of approximately 6 mm diameter. The wells were equidistant from each other and the edge of the plate [10]. The wells were then filled with 50 µl of each ethanolic extract at a concentration of 160 mg/ml, 80 mg/ml and 40 mg/ml. Also, concentration of 200 µg/ml of ciprofloxacin and 200 µg/ml DMSO were introduced into other wells as positive and negative controls, respectively with the aid of micropipette. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Antibacterial activity was determined by measuring the zone of inhibition surrounding the well. The zones of inhibition were then measured, recorded and compared with standard control (ciprofloxacin). The assays were carried out under aseptic conditions. Each antibacterial assay was performed in at least three times. Mean values (± standard deviation) are reported in this study.

Determination of MIC and MBC

Preparation of the solution of extracts

The stock ethanolic extracts solutions were prepared by dissolving 59 mg of each extracts in 200 µl of 10% dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and mixed with 1600 µl of Mueller Hinton Broth, to give the final concentration of 8192 µg/ml and serially diluted two fold to obtain the concentration ranges from 256-8192 µg/ml for the extract and 0.5-64 µg/ml for ciprofloxacin. 100 µl of each concentration was added in 96 wells plates containing 100 µl of MHB and inoculums standardized at 1.5×10^8 CFU/ml. Negative growth controls were included in every test. The plates were covered with a sterile plate sealer, then agitated to mix the contents of the wells using a plate shaker and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The MIC of each sample was detected following addition (40 µl) of 2% p-iodonitrotetrazolium chloride and incubation at 37°C for 30 minutes [11]. Viable microorganisms reduced the yellow dye to a pink colour. MIC was defined as the lowest sample concentration that prevented this change and exhibited complete inhibition of bacterial growth. For the determination of MBC, a portion of liquid (50 µl) from each well that showed no change in color was placed on MHB (150 µl each new 96 wells plates) and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The lowest concentration that yielded no growth after this subculturing was taken as the MBC. MBC/MIC was calculated to determine if the extract is bactericidal or bacteriostatic, according to [12].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Antibacterial assay

Wells diffusion assay

According to [13], plants were the sole source of active principles capable of curing man's ailments before the development of chemistry and synthesis of organic compounds in the 19th century. The details of antibacterial activity of plants used in this study are shown in Table 2 & 3. Of the 10 plant extracts tested, nine plant extracts were found to have antibacterial activity against at least one of the bacteria strains tested with inhibition zones ranging from 7.5 to 24 mm at concentration of 40 mg/ml, 80 mg/ml and 160 mg/ml. This could be attributed to several secondary metabolites present in them [3]. Moreover, all active tested plant extracts inhibited growth of the bacteria strains in an increasing trend as their concentrations. The extracts of *Dissotis perkinsiae* did not show any activity. However, negative results do not indicate the

absence of bioactive constituents, or that the plant is inactive. Active compounds may be present in insufficient quantities in the extracts to show activity with the dose levels employed [14]. Lack of activity can thus only be proven by using large doses [15]. Alternatively, if the active principle is present in high quantities, there could be other constituents exerting antagonistic effects or negating the positive effects of the bioactive agents [16]. With no antibacterial activity, extract may be active against other bacterial species which were not tested [17].

Out of the 9 active plants species, *Salmonella typhi*, *S. paratyphi* B and *S. paratyphi* A were inhibited by 6, 4 and 3 plant species, respectively. Among different extracts, *Senna alata* were the most potent active extract against both species of *Salmonella*. Whereas, *Pseudarthria confertiflora* extracts displayed profound antibacterial activity against *Salmonella typhi* and *S. paratyphi* B with 23.5 mm and 17.5 mm zone of inhibition respectively at concentration of 160 mg/ml (Table 2). The observed antisalmonella activity of *Senna alata* agrees with the finding of [18] on broad spectrum antimicrobial activity. *Pseudarthria confertiflora* has not been reported in literature before for use in the treatment of infectious diseases. However, *Pseudarthria viscida*, a member of family Fabaceae and genus *Pseudarthria* has been reported for use as an antimicrobial agent [19]. Chemotaxonomically certain families and genera are known to possess specific secondary metabolites which tend to be similarly active in terms of their medicinal properties [20]. *Staphylococcus aureus* showed sensitivity to seven plant extracts with diameters of zone of inhibition ranging from 8-18.5 mm at concentration of 40 mg/ml, 80 mg/ml and 160 mg/ml (Table 2). The anti-*Staphylococcus* activity of some of these plants has been studied previously. For instance, the ethanol leaves extract of *Carica papaya* [21] and aqueous leaves extract of *Senna alata* [22] were found to inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus* strains. Eight out of ten plants screened (Table 2) showed activity against *Enterococcus faecalis*; the highest activity was observed with the extracts from *Senna alata* with inhibition zone of 23.5 mm in the concentration 160 mg/ml, followed by *Pseudarthria confertiflora* (16.5 mm), *Aspilia africana* and *Crassocephalum mannii* with inhibition zones 15, 14 mm in the same concentration, respectively. The antibacterial effect of *Senna alata* and *Aspilia africana* were demonstrated by previous workers [22, 23]. *Escherichia coli* showed sensitivity to seven plants extracts (Table 2); *Senna alata* and *Stereospermum accuminatissimum* were the most active tested plants. The antibacterial effect of *Senna alata* is in agreement with previous workers [22, 24, 25]. However, antibacterial activity of *Stereospermum accuminatissimum* is reported here for the first time. Five medicinal plants species extracts were observed to be biologically active, and cause growth inhibition of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Table 2). Whereas, only *Pseudarthria confertiflora* and *Senna alata* could be good leads for pharmacological discoveries according to their diameters of inhibition zones. The extracts of *Carica papaya*, *Pseudarthria confertiflora* and *Senna alata* exhibited promoting anti *Klebsiella pneumoniae* activity. The results of some of these plants were not surprising. The antibacterial activity of *Carica papaya* and *Senna alata* is well known [21, 24, 25, 26] and recent studies have reported the antibacterial activity of extracts

from one species of *Pseudarthria* (*P. viscida*) [19]. Noteworthy, the most susceptible bacterium was *Enterococcus faecalis* following by *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. While, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Salmonella paratyphi* A and *S. paratyphi* B were the most resistant bacteria tested since only three or four plant extracts had showed inhibitory activity against them. This kind of differences in susceptibility between the bacterial strains against antibacterial substances in plants extracts may be explained by the differences in cell wall composition and/or inheritance genes on plasmids that can be easily be transferred among bacterial strains [27]. In fact, the

broad spectrum activity was shown by *Stereospermum accuminatissimum*, *Pseudarthria confertiflora*, *Senna alata*, *Carica papaya*, *Dioscorea dumetorum*, *Aspilia africana* and *Crassocephalum mannii* at concentration of 160 mg/ml. Among these, *Senna alata* exhibited a strong activity against the 8 bacteria strains studied with diameter inhibition zones ranging from 14.5-24 mm. Whereas, *Bidens pilosa*, *Carica papaya* and *Pseudarthria confertiflora* showed activity against 7 bacteria species studied. These broad spectrum plants belonging of the plants that exhibit a wide range of biological activities including antiviral, fungicide and antibacterial activities [21, 28, 29, 26, 30, 31].

Table 2: Antibacterial activity of plant extracts.

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Antibacterial activity against (Diameter of inhibition)									
Plant species and antibiotic	Concentration	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	<i>S. paratyphi</i> A	<i>S. paratyphi</i> B	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
<i>Acmella caulirhiza</i> <i>Delile</i>	40 mg/ml	-	-	-	-	0±00	0±00	0±00	-
	80 mg/ml	-	-	-	-	8±0.82	0±00	10±00	-
	160 mg/ml	-	-	-	-	10.5±0.41	8.5±0.41	11.5±0.41	-
<i>Aspilia africana</i> (<i>Pers</i>) <i>C.D.</i> <i>Adams</i>	40 mg/ml	-	-	-	8.5±0.41	8.5±0.41	0±00	-	-
	80 mg/ml	-	-	-	9±0.82	12.5±0.41	7.5±0.41	-	-
	160 mg/ml	-	-	-	11±0.82	15±00	10.5±0.41	-	-
<i>Bidens pilosa</i> <i>Linn.</i>	40 mg/ml	10.5±1.22	10±00	9±00	10.5±0.41	9±0.82	7.5±0.41	0±00	-
	80 mg/ml	12±0.82	10.5±0.41	10±00	11.5±0.41	11±0.82	9.5±0.41	0±00	-
	160 mg/ml	13±0.82	12±0.82	12.5±0.41	12.5±0.41	12.5±0.41	10.5±0.41	9±0.82	-
<i>Crassocephalum mannii</i> (<i>Hook.</i>) <i>F.</i> <i>Milne-Redh</i>	40 mg/ml	11±00	-	-	9±00	8.5±0.41	-	-	-
	80 mg/ml	13±0.82	-	-	10.5±0.41	10.5±0.41	-	-	-
	160 mg/ml	15±0.82	-	-	13±0.82	14±0.82	-	-	-
<i>Stereospermum accuminatissimum</i> <i>K. Schum.</i>	40 mg/ml	-	-	-	-	9±0.82	11.5±0.41	8±00	-
	80 mg/ml	-	-	-	-	11±0.82	13±0.82	10±00	-
	160 mg/ml	-	-	-	-	12.5±1.22	16±0.82	11±0.82	-
<i>Carica papaya</i> <i>Linn.</i>	40 mg/ml	8.5±0.41	9±0.82	0±00	11±0.82	9±0.82	9±0.82	-	0±00
	80 mg/ml	10±00	11±0.82	9.5±0.41	13±00	10.5±0.41	9.5±1.22	-	8.5±0.41
	160 mg/ml	12±00	12±0.82	11±0.82	16±0.82	12.5±0.41	12.5±0.41	-	11±0.82
<i>Dioscorea dumetorum</i> (<i>Kunth</i>) <i>Pax</i>	40 mg/ml	0±00	-	-	9.5±0.41	-	-	-	-
	80 mg/ml	9.5±0.41	-	-	11.5±0.41	-	-	-	-
	160 mg/ml	11±0.82	-	-	14.5±0.41	-	-	-	-
<i>Pseudarthria confertiflora</i> (<i>A. Rich.</i>) <i>Bak</i>	40 mg/ml	11.5±0.41	-	11±0.81	8±00	11.5±0.41	9.5±0.41	11±0.82	0±00
	80 mg/ml	15±0.82	-	13.5±1.22	9±00	12.5±0.41	10.5±0.41	13.5±0.41	10±0.82
	160 mg/ml	23.5±1.22	-	17.5±0.41	11.5±0.41	16.5±0.41	13±0.82	17±1.63	12.5±0.41
<i>Senna alata</i>	40 mg/ml	10.5±0.41	12.5±0.41	10.5±0.41	11±0.82	16.5±0.41	10.5±0.41	10±00	11.5±0.41

(Linn.) Roxb.	80 mg/ml	17.5±0.41	17.5±0.41	13.5±0.41	14±0.82	18.5±0.41	12.5±0.41	12±00	14±00
	160 mg/ml	20.5±0.41	24±0.82	22.5±2.04	18.5±0.41	23.5±1.22	16.5±0.41	14.5±0.41	19±0.82
<i>Dissotis perkinsiae</i> Gilg.	40-160 mg/ml	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ciprofloxacin	200 µg/ml	30±0.82	28.5±1.22	30±1.63	27±0.82	32±1.63	32±0.82	29±0.82	26±1.63

The unit for zone of inhibition is mm; Values are means ± SD of 3 different sets of experiments

Determination of MIC and MBC

The MIC and MBC value obtained using the broth microdilution method is given in Table 3. The MICs ranged from 256 to 8192 µg/ml with the lowest MIC of 256 µg/ml recorded for *Pseudarthria confertiflora* extract on *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Low MIC is an indication of high efficacy of the plant extract while high MIC may indicate low efficacy or possible development of resistance by the microorganisms to the antibacterial [18]. The MBCs (lowest concentration that killed the bacteria) showed that 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 and 1 plants extracts were bactericidal against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella paratyphi A* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* respectively (Table 3). This, therefore, shows that our plants extracts contains substances that can inhibit the growth of some microorganisms. Other workers have also shown that extracts of some plants inhibited the growth of various microorganisms at different concentrations [32, 33]. The lowest MBC recorded was 1024 µg/ml with two bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) in two plants extracts namely *Carica papaya* and *Senna alata*. However, most of the plants extracts were bacteriostatic with a few having broad spectrum bacteriostatic activity, while a smaller number were bactericidal (Table 3). This suggests that most of these plants, when used traditionally

as antibacterials, inhibit bacterial growth without necessarily killing the bacteria. Overall, our results show that these medicinal plants have selective activity, being bacteriostatic or bactericidal.

Previous phytochemical studies of the more active plants showed that *Senna alata* contained phenols, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, sterols, flavonoids and carbohydrates [25]; *Pseudarthria confertiflora* contained alkaloids, flavonoids, polyphenols, triterpens, sterols and saponins while *Stereospermum acuminatissimum* contained all these compounds except alkaloids [34]. *Carica papaya* contained folic acids, vitamin B₁₂, alkaloids, saponins, glycosides, tannins, anthraquinones, flavonoids and antioxidants [35]. *Aspilia africana* contains alkaloids, tannins, cardenolides, and glycosides [36]. Some of these compounds are likely to be active against certain bacteria, this may account for the traditional uses of these plants.

It was noticed that Ciprofloxacin, which served as positive control, produced the highest antibacterial activity on both pathogens with zone of inhibition ranging from 26 to 32 mm and MIC ranging from 0.5 to 64 µg/ml (Table 3). The comparison of the activity of our plants extracts with ciprofloxacin, showed that ciprofloxacin is more active than our plants extracts, as confirmed by other workers [37].

Table 3: MICs and MBCs of plants against bacteria in µg/ml

Plant species and antibiotic	Antibacterial activity against															
	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>		<i>S. paratyphi A</i>		<i>S. paratyphi B</i>		<i>Sataphylococcus aureus</i>		<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>		<i>Escherichia coli</i>		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>		<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	
	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC
<i>Acmella caulirhiza</i> Delile	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	4096	8192 (B)	nd	nd (Bs)	8192	nd (Bs)	nd	nd
<i>Aspilia africana</i> (Pers) C.D. Adams	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	2048	8192 (B)	1024	2048 (B)	1024	nd (Bs)	nd	nd	nd	nd
<i>Bidens pilosa</i> Linn.	512	2048(B)	nd	nd (Bs)	nd	nd	4096	4096 (B)	2048	4096 (B)	1024	4096 (B)	nd	nd (Bs)	nd	nd
<i>Crassocephalum mannii</i> (Hook. F) Milne-Redh	2048	nd (Bs)	nd	nd	nd	nd	4096	nd (Bs)	nd	nd (Bs)	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
<i>Stereospermum acuminatissimum</i> K. Schum.	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd (Bs)	nd	nd (Bs)	1024	8192 (Bs)	nd	nd (Bs)	nd	nd

<i>Carica papaya</i> Linn.	1024	2048 (B)	nd	nd (Bs)	nd	nd	512	1024 (B)	1024	4096 (B)	2048	4096 (B)	nd	nd	nd	nd
<i>Dioscorea dumetorum</i> (Kunth) Pax	1024	8192 (Bs)	nd	nd	nd	nd	2048	8192 (B)	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
<i>Pseudarthria confertiflora</i> (A. Rich.) Bak	2048	8192 (B)	nd	nd	2048	2048 (B)	nd	nd (Bs)	1024	8192 (Bs)	1024	8192 (Bs)	1024	8192 (Bs)	256	4096 (Bs)
<i>Senna alata</i> (Linn.) Roxb.	1024	nd (Bs)	512	4096 (Bs)	512	4096 (Bs)	nd	nd (Bs)	512	8192 (Bs)	nd	nd (Bs)	8192	nd (Bs)	1024	4096 (B)
<i>Dissotis perkinsiae</i> Gilg.	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Ciprofloxacin	64	128 (B)	32	64 (B)	32	64 (B)	64	128 (B)	32	64 (B)	0.5	64 (Bs)	64	256 (B)	64	128 (B)

MIC: Minimum inhibition concentration; MBC: Minimum bactericidal concentration; (-): No activity; nd: Not defined; B: Bactericidal; Bs: Bacteriostatic

CONCLUSION

Medicinal plants are used in many parts of Cameroon for the treatment of infectious diseases. Our results offer a scientific basis for the traditional use of plant extracts. *Senna alata* were found effective against *Salmonella typhi*, *S. paratyphi* A, *S. paratyphi* B, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* which are associated with enteric fever, abdominal pains, skin, wounds, respiratory tract and urinary tract infections. Also, *Bidens pilosa*, *Carica papaya* and *Pseudarthria confertiflora* were active against seven of the bacteria strains tested. These plants could serve as a cheap source of antibacterial constituent for the treatment of infectious diseases. Thus, research on these plants should be encouraged.

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